

ScamGuard: Image-based Identification App for Phishing and Open Attachment Messages Using Variants of Convolutional Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT

The growing prevalence of scam messages in the digital landscape poses a significant threat, particularly in the Philippines where a large proportion of the population is active on social media. These messages are becoming increasingly sophisticated and difficult to distinguish, making the development of effective scam detection techniques essential for protection against scammers. Text-based scam detection models developed in the past years are good at classifying text messages, but are disadvantageous because users may accidentally click on links which redirect to illegitimate sources or malwares. This study discusses the development of an image-based scam detection app powered by Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). A comparative analysis based on Traditional Learning Approach and Transfer Learning Approach was conducted. Results showed that the Transfer Learning Approach based on Mobile Net V2 architecture yielded an accuracy score of 92% while the Traditional Learning Approach achieved an accuracy score of 91%. The best formulated model was integrated into an app, here we call 'ScamGuard'. The app enables users to upload screenshots of messages and classify them as scam or non-scam. Additionally, the app features a chatbot with predefined responses to address users' queries related to scams. By integrating the complex architecture of a CNN model into an app, convenience is provided to the users for identifying scam messages allowing them to make informed decisions before engaging with potentially scam messages.

Keywords: *Phishing, Scam Detection, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Transfer Learning Models*

I. INTRODUCTION

Technological developments in computers and mobile devices have increased accessibility to the Internet, which has made text messaging the most widely used form of communication. (Shropshire, 2016). This development offers advantages, including the convenience of reaching people. Instead of only being reachable when there was a landline phone nearby, we became continually accessible, regardless of the time and location. This advantage changes the way people interact socially and has increasingly dominated communication systems, making it crucial for sharing information and connecting with others. Although this kind of communication has made things much more flexible and accessible, it has also led to the emergence of new problems - cybercrimes. Cybercrime has become increasingly prevalent in the Philippines. Recent surveys have shown that there was a 68.98 percent increase in cybercrimes in 2023, with 19,472 incidents compared to 11,523 cases in 2022 (PNP, 2023). One of the fastest growing cybercrimes considered in the country is 'Identity theft'. It refers to an attacker using a person's identity to steal and use that person's personal information (such as bank account information, social security number, credit card number, etc.) for that person's gain, not only for money theft but also for other crimes (Arachchilage and Love, 2014). Although cybercriminals have improved their techniques, their preferred method of information theft remains social engineering-based attacks. One of the social engineering crimes where the attacker can perform identity theft is called a phishing attack.

Phishing has been one of the biggest concerns as many internet users fall victim to it (Alkhalil et al., 2021). Phishing is a form of online identity theft that uses social engineering techniques to deceive individuals into divulging sensitive information (Fox, 2021). The term phishing is derived from the word 'fishing', in which an attacker uses "bait" to lure the victim and then "fishes" for the personal information they want to steal (Alabdan, 2020). Phishing attackers, commonly referred to as phishers, target individuals by pretending to be legitimate companies, appealing to users to visit a fake Website by sending them fake messages, and obtain the victim's personal information such as user name, password, national security ID, etc.

Fig 1. Phishing Attack Process (Source: Cloudflare)

Figure 1 illustrates the general process of a phishing attack that contains four phases. A phishing attack begins with the phishers sending the victim a fake message. These messages are meticulously constructed to appear legitimate, using language, urgency, and logos and to lure victims. The message sent to a victim contains a link that goes directly to a phishing website. Upon clicking the link, the victims are directed to the phishing website where logging in personal information is required. After gaining access to the victim's login credentials, the phishers can enter their accounts without authorization to make use of sensitive and personal data for illegal activities such as financial scams or identity theft. Phishing attacks have various types. Some of the well-known types of phishing attacks include SMS/Smishing, Vishing, and Social Media Phishing (Parker, 2020).

A. Types of Phishing Attacks

SMS/Smishing

SMS phishing, or smishing, is an attack targeted to mobile devices in which the attacker sends text messages containing malicious links to the user (Mishra & Soni, 2019). The attacker aims to steal sensitive user data like bank account details, passwords, user credentials, credit card details, etc through this message. Through this, the attacker prompts the user to click on the link provided in the SMS. Once clicked, victims are directed to a fake website where they may be asked to enter personal information or download a malicious app, unknowingly compromising their security.

Fig 2. Examples of SMS Phishing/Smishing

In the first message (left side), the sender encourages the user by offering 100% cashback benefits for registering and depositing P100. They include popular games such as JILI, FC, and PG to make the offer more enticing. On the other hand, the second message (right side) promises a 5,000 PHP reward for joining an online gambling platform. It promises to feature 24-hour cash in/out choices and the opportunity to win a huge amount of money. Both messages focused on people's desire for rewards and money. Moreover, both also contained a link that directs users to an unknown website.

Call Phishing/Vishing

Call phishing, or vishing, occurs when attackers deceived users by impersonating trusted organizations, such as banks, government agencies, and even famous personalities, during phone calls (Choi et al., 2017). These attackers use social engineering tactics to manipulate victims into

sharing sensitive information, such as account numbers, passwords, or social security numbers. They may claim there is a problem with the victim's account or offer false rewards or services to gain the victim's trust and compliance.

Fig 3. Examples of Call Phishing/Vishing

Figure 3 shows the examples of Call Phishing/ Vishing. In the first message (left side), the user is informed that they have won a large amount of money from the "GMA Kapuso Foundation" and is instructed to contact a certain person to claim their reward. Similarly, the other message (right side) congratulates the user on winning money and requests to call a particular person to claim the prize. Both messages mentioned well-known personalities and organizations to create a sense of legitimacy, making the users' actually call those particular people. Once the user called, an interview will be conducted regarding their personal information. They may also request an advance payment or fees on pretenses, stating it is required so that the reward could be released.

Social Network Phishing

Phishing through Social Network Services (SNS) such as Facebook, Twitter, Snapchat, Instagram, etc. involves the creation of fake profiles or pages on social networking platforms to deceive users (Frauenstein & Flowerday, 2016). Attackers may pose as friends, celebrities, or reputable organizations to establish credibility and gain victims' trust. They often entice victims with offers of giveaways, prizes, or romantic relationships. Once victims engage with the fraudulent profiles, attackers may request personal information or financial assistance, leading to identity theft or financial loss.

Fig 4. Example of Social Media Phishing

An example of a social media phishing is the DSWD scam in the Philippines. Links to the purported online registration form for this message have been spreading on Facebook and Messenger. Upon clicking on the link provided, users are directed to a website purporting to be from DSWD, where they will be asked to answer a questionnaire for a chance to receive a P7,000 cash assistance. This message offers users a government subsidy or money, but in reality, the attackers present fake information to attract users to click on the link and have their information taken. The Philippines has witnessed a significant increase in social media users, with projections indicating a gradual rise from 2024 to 2028, adding nearly 7.7 million users at a growth rate of 8.93%. On average, Filipinos spend more than 4 hours and 15 minutes per day on their phones, implying that more people are sharing their personal information (Statistica Search Department, 2023). Reports show a 47.2% increase in phishing attempts in 2022 compared to the previous year (Zscaler ThreatLabz, 2023), highlighting the persistent threat posed by phishers, who continue to target more Filipinos.

B. Scam Detection

The growing number of phishing attacks has opened up new opportunities for phishers to exploit weaknesses and defraud individuals. However, the field of scam detection has developed various techniques to combat the threat of phishing through text-based classification techniques, such as Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning (ML).

Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a text-based technique that focuses on interactions between machines and human language (Sanadi & Bhat, 2022). In scam detection, NLP enables computers to read, evaluate, and analyze textual information to detect patterns and indications of fraudulent activities. Its algorithms can evaluate huge quantities of textual data from SMS, chat logs, and social media postings to extract significant information about possible scam. This involves recognizing keywords, phrases, or language patterns that are frequently connected with fraudulent behavior. Furthermore, NLP-based message filtering systems can immediately evaluate whether a message received by an individual is legitimate or suspicious based on its content, phishing attempts and fraudulent requests for sensitive information.

Machine Learning (ML)

Machine Learning is a popular method that is widely used for scam detection (Basit, 2021). This technique focuses on developing algorithms that enable computer systems to learn and make predictions or decisions based on the features of the data. With this, the model will undergo training to detect phishing behaviors based on those features (Zhu et al., 2020). In other words, machine learning algorithms learn from historical data patterns and use that knowledge to make predictions or decisions on new, unseen data. This technique performs well with large data sets and reaches more than 99% accuracy, making it the most effective method (Alkawaz et al., 2021). Machine learning models provide the best alternative to traditional methods in the field of text classification. Research in the field of scam detection has developed various text-based message-identification techniques, including text analysis (Dastjerdi et al., 2019; Oladimeji, 2019), link analysis (Shekokar, 2015; Hajgude & Raha 2012), and header analysis (Yuk, 2021; Hassan & Hussain, 2017). Text analysis is the process of identifying patterns and trends while also extracting information from unstructured and massive data (Raval & Lohia, 2021). The utilization of text analysis allows poring over message body content to determine whether it contains any suspicious

content (Dastjerdi et al., 2019). Link analysis, on the other hand, identifies whether a message is legitimate or a fraudulent attempt by looking up information about the links contained in it. This generally entails verifying that the Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of the website to which the user is sent upon clicking the link indeed corresponds to the link provided in the email (Park and Taylor, 2013). Lastly, header analysis determines whether a message is a scam by looking through its header content. In this analysis, the "from" field of the email is usually verified to match the real sender, and the IP address from which the email was sent is verified against fraudulent blacklists (Kim, 2018).

Text Analysis

Dastjerdi et al. (2019) compared the precision of two data mining methods in detecting manager's fraud risk using text analysis, emphasizing the importance of text data over financial statements and the superiority of methods with a binary-dependent variable. The study involved analyzing board's reports using the CVX and LASSO methods to detect the manager's fraud risk index, with the LASSO method showing higher precision. The precision of detecting a manager's high fraud risk index using data mining methods ranged from 82.55% to 91.25%, with LASSO method showing higher precision compared to CVX method. Oladimeji (2019) discussed the use of text mining and machine learning for phished message detection, the superiority of machine learning methods over other techniques, and the high classification accuracy of Naive Bayes in identifying phishing messages. The study involved text mining and the use of three machine learning techniques (Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbor, and Support Vector Machine) for identifying phishing messages, with Naive Bayes showing the highest classification accuracy. Machine learning methods outperformed traditional phishing message detection techniques, with Naive Bayes achieving the highest classification accuracy of 99.0%.

Link Analysis

Shekokar et al. (2015) proposed a phishing detection and prevention approach combining URL-based and Web Page similarity-based detection. URL-based phishing detection involves extraction of the actual URL (to which the website is actually directed) and the visual URL (which is visible to the user). LinkGuard Algorithm is used to analyze the two URLs and finally depending on the result produced by the algorithm the procedure proceeds to the next phase. If phishing is not detected or Phishing possibility is predicted in URL-based detection, the algorithm proceeds to the visual similarity-based detection. A novel technique to visually compare a suspicious page with the legitimate one is presented. Hajgude & Ragma (2012) emphasized the use of URL and textual content analysis for anti-phishing email classification, and the proposed technique involving blacklist, white list, and heuristic analysis to increase accuracy and reduce false positives. The study involves a technique that combines blacklist, white list, and heuristic methods for detecting phishing emails, with a focus on textual analysis. The detection of phishing messages is based on DNS presence in the blacklist and pattern matching with existing phishing DNS. Overall, the proposed technique of combining blacklist, white list, and heuristic techniques based on textual and URL analysis shows promise in accurately detecting phishing emails and reducing false positives.

Header Analysis

Yuk et al. (2021) proposed a malware detection system using static analysis and stacking methods to effectively classify malware in the face of increasing threats posed by new strains of

malware. The methodology involves proposing a malware detection system using machine learning algorithms and static analysis of PE headers, building on previous research on DLLs, APIs, and malware features for detection, and utilizing various machine learning models for classification and detection of malware families. The malware detection system proposed in this study consists of the following steps: data preprocessing, feature extraction, model learning, and model evaluation. The proposed malware detection system achieved a 95.2% malware detection rate, outperforming existing single model-based detection systems. Furthermore, the system can quickly and accurately classify malware or ordinary files.

Hassan & Hussain (2017) proposed an effective machine learning approach for filtering spam messages through identifying potential header and body fields. The Machine learning dataset used is a combination of open source spambase and custom developed dataset for header fields. Weka in combination with naïve-bayes classification technique is applied using machine learning based dataset encompassing certain header field-based attributes. A mail client is designed in asp.net, which is used as an interface that separates the header and body of the mail. The effectiveness of the proposed machine learning approach was compared with one that does not use machine learning approach and it was found the proposed approach performed better when using machine-learning approach.

Text-based approach is one of the most popular approaches for detecting scam messages (Shehnepoor, 2020). However, this approach has disadvantages. Text-based scam filters primarily concentrate on textual content ignoring visual components such as photos and graphics that are included in phishing messages (Zhang, 2011). It is also best at detecting phishing attacks in English and works poorly at detecting phishing attacks in Oriental languages. Such limitations greatly reduce the potential coverage of a scam filter because a scam attack can occur in any language (Lou, 2013). This greatly affects the identification of text messages, since most cybercriminals in the Philippines usually use the Filipino language to scam their fellow Filipinos. Another drawback of a text-based scam filter is that it requires copying and pasting text messages for users to determine their legitimacy. There are instances in which a user copies and pastes a text message; malicious link or attachment might be accidentally clicked, providing the attacker with an opportunity to deceive the users. In social media, particularly on Facebook, clicking a malicious link will lead users to an external site where they must download a flash player update to view the attachment (Gonzales, 2021). Instead of attachment, the user is directed to a malware infection, endangering their personal information and possibly leading to the user's Facebook account being taken over. The user account also sends private messages and publishes posts tagging their friends on Facebook, people in their Facebook groups, and users with whom they have interacted without being aware of it. For example, a user receives a message on Facebook from a friend. The message appears to be a regular conversation, but it includes a link that says, "Click here to see our latest photos together." The user, trusting his friend, clicks the link to view the supposed photos. However, instead of being directed to a photo album, the user is taken to a website where downloading a "Flash Player update" is necessary to view the content. Unaware of the potential danger, the user proceeds with the download. However, instead of a legitimate Flash Player update, the user unknowingly installs malware on his device. This malware can now access the user's personal information, such as login credentials, banking details, and sensitive data stored on his device. The malware also gains control of the user's Facebook account. It starts sending private messages to his friends, posting links on his timeline, and tagging random users in his posts. Moreover, these posts and messages could help spread malware, as people are more likely to click the link if they come from someone they know.

Fig 5. Example of a malware infected Facebook account

Figure 5 shows an example of a malware infected facebook account. The posts of the account mainly contain sexual contents, particularly those showing “sexy girls”. This is a common strategy that attackers employ on social networking sites like Facebook. These posts are intended to grab users' attention through sensationalism and exploit their curiosity or desires, eventually leading them to click on malicious links. These are not only unethical but also potentially harmful. Clicking these posts can lead users to malware downloads or fraudulent schemes targeting personal information.

Fig 6. Facebook Page of a Private School

Figure 6 shows another example of a malware infected account. A private Catholic institution in Cagayan de Oro City, was victimized by a phishing attack on its official Facebook page. The page’s admin must have clicked an unknown link, resulting in the download of a malware. This malware enabled the page to post explicit sexual content, primarily videos of girls.

Up until today, the page has not been removed and continues to upload inappropriate contents. The aforementioned concerns underscore the importance of leveraging other approaches, rather than text-based ones, that are also capable of efficiently extracting relevant characteristics from a diverse array of scam messages to differentiate them from legitimate ones.

C. Image Classification

Images can be used as input features for classification. Image-based classification is an important scam detection approach that categorizes or identifies images based on their visual content. This approach is particularly effective in cases when fraud incorporates visual aspects, such as phishing messages with fake logos or attachments containing malicious content. The essential components of image-based classification include feature extraction and the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs). Feature extraction is crucial for capturing relevant information from images (Gawali, 2023; Hassan, 2023), and CNNs are specifically designed for this task, enabling the processing of visual data (Chen, 2022).

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), a machine learning algorithm, have recently drawn the attention of many researchers studying image classification tasks because they outperform other traditional machine learning algorithms in terms of learning efficiency and produce more meaningful and practical representations that lead to optimal results (Chouiekh & Haj, 2018). CNNs are effective in image classification, particularly when used as feature extractors in data-scarce visual searches (Abdallah, 2016). CNNs also excel in identifying patterns in the input image, including lines, gradients, and loops. This characteristic provides CNN with immense power in computer vision (Wood, 2021). Owing to its capabilities, this approach can be used as an alternative method for identifying scam messages.

Transfer Learning

Transfer learning models as its names suggest is a machine learning technique in which previously trained machine learning models that are usually large and complex are used later without the requirement of re-training from the scratch. Contrary to the traditional ways of fine-tuning models, a technique called transfer learning allows the use and tuning of existing models without having to manually adjust the model's parameters. This way is not only the most time-saving but also effective in resource-poor settings. For example, the knowledge used from domain X is being applied in domain Y with the help of knowledge gained from the previous learnt domain. This stored information can be subsequently built on by unfreezing some layers, enabling the model to learn specific classification problems. Transfer learning involves many models which are tailored to diverse classification problems dependent on the conditions. Our goal is to build an application that can scan screenshots to detect scam messages. With this goal, we target two specific versions of the MobileNet transfer learning model against the performance metrics of a custom CNN model. Mobile Net Transfer Learning models originated from Google, MobileNet which is a free open-source model for computer vision/CNN uses a depth wise separable convolution, which helps to significantly decrease the parameter count as compared to other models and thus can be an effective lightweight deep neural network suitable for integration on smartphones without demanding extensive computational resources. This paper introduces an image-based approach to scam detection using classification techniques with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and transfer learning models using our own Philippines based data set. Unlike traditional text-based

methods our approach harnesses the power of visual patterns to identify potentially scam messages.

The following are the specific objectives of the study;

1. Train the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model using Philippine-based scam and non-scam messages dataset.
2. Fine-tune the model's hyperparameters such as learning rate and batch size, add dropout layers and L2 regularization to optimize performance and improve generalization capabilities, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of scam detection.
3. Test and evaluate the model to assess its accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and kappa score.
4. Compare the three variants of CNN models (MobileNet V2, MobileNet V3 (small), Custom CNN) to determine the best performing model to use for the application.
5. Integrate the best performing model into the "Scam Guard" Android application, providing users with a user-friendly interface for offline scam detection.
6. Integrate an offline chatbot powered by a JSON algorithm for extra protection against scams.

In summary, this study offers the following contributions:

1. Address the limitations of scam detection through text-based classification techniques by leveraging image-based classification techniques.
2. Provide insights on the efficacy and reliability of using image-based identification techniques in scam detection.
3. By using an image-based algorithm to create a scam filter, users are only required to provide a screenshot of the message they want to predict, significantly lowering the risk of accidentally clicking on malicious links within the message and thus limiting the potential spread of malware infections.
4. This study not only develops an image-based model to detect scam messages in the philippine context but also integrates the model into an application, becoming the first image-based scam detection application to be made entirely from a philippine based data set.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Formulation of the Classification Model for Fraud Detection

The development of an image-based scam detection model requires a complex procedure that includes some important steps. This process can be generally categorized into two main formats both of which encompass a set of unique procedures. The primary step in this process is data collection. It entails collecting data that will be used to train the model and for testing purposes as well. The data could include screenshots, both of scam and non-scam messages. Based on the gathered information, the next step is to prepare the data. This entails cleaning the data by deleting images that are not important or unnecessary such as blurred images, wrong formats etc. the data set is also organized by allocating specific folders and labels to the data set. Once data is ready, it is divided into three equal parts which are training data, test data, and validation. Training data is employed in training a model, the testing data is applied in evaluating the model during the training process, and the validation data is for verifying the model once it is trained. After the data has been ready, the model that could identify if a screenshot is classified as a scam or non-scam.

Fig 7. Flow chart of the model creation

The model utilizes machine learning algorithms that allows it to process the training data and make predictions. At last, the performance of the model will be assessed to verify its reliability. This process entails analyzing the machine learning model performance by examining how it classifies the screenshots on the basis of the test and validation datasets. Evaluation of the model can be made by using metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, MCC and F1 score.

Fig 8. Sample Images in the data set

A.1. Data Collection

The data collection process includes collecting screenshots of scam and non-scam messages in a form of screenshots coming from different sources namely: facebook-messenger, whatsapp, telegram, and from the normal messaging app. We collected our data through the people who were scammed and the people who received scam messages. A total of 1,618 screenshots of non-scam instances and 1,544 screenshots for scam instances were gathered for a total of 3162 screenshots for the main data set. A snippet of the collected data together with its labels are presented in figure 8.

A.2. Data Preprocessing

After the collection of data, we preprocessed the data for training. The preprocessing steps include: **(1) Label-encoding:** to do this we used a ‘main-set’ folder as the main folder and two sub-folders namely scam and non-scam. The sub-folders are the main labels for each class separately. The classes are isolated so that there is no mixing of data. **(2) Data-cleaning:** checking for the images one-by-one with the help of a algorithm created in python, which loops through the dataset, to make sure that there are no loaded images which are low-quality or unsupported formats such as: GIF (Graphics Interchange Format), TIFF (Tagged Image File Format), RAW (Camera RAW Image Formats), DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine), and other unsupported formats **(3) Image-resizing:** once the images have been confirmed to have met the quality and formatting standards, we resize the image to a specific size, e.g. 224x224 or 256x256, to enable the model to train the images consistently and efficiently. **(4) Normalization:** a RGB image file has a pixel value of 0 to 256 for each red, green and blue (RGB) channel. The normalization function breaks down values to meet model needs (for instance, the CNN model divides each value by 255.0 and gets a scale down between 0 and 1). This way the model can efficiently update the weight since it has the same range of pixel values.

A.3. Data Partitioning

Fig 9. Data partition

Following preprocessing of images to conform to the input format of training the CNN model, we split the data-set into 70% for training or 2212 images, 20% for validation or 631 images and the rest 10% for model testing or 315 images. Allocating 70% of the dataset for training is vital as during the training time the model needs more data than the validation such that it allows the model to learn more intricate and sophisticated patterns or features of an image.

A.4. Model Development

Convolutional Neural Network or CNN is a type of machine learning algorithm that takes images or in some classification problems a text as the input and produces a prediction number or a range of numbers as an output, depending on the number of classes these numbers can often represent a class type. A CNN model is structured in several layers having different functionality in network architecture. The first step of the model is to accept preprocessed images in the form of a matrix with pixel values as input data. What will come next is Convolutional layers which will be responsible for applying learnable filters that will localize patterns and features in the image inputs. Following the convolutional layers the output is also processed by an activation function that injects nonlinearity into the model which assists the model in learning complicated patterns in the data. These Pooling Layers will down sample the feature maps but retain only important features while reducing the spatial dimensions with operations like max pooling and average pooling. Following the low-level features extraction operations from input images, the fully connected layers will convert high-level features derived from the previous stages to make predictions. There are three layers, which are connected by a dense layer, which enables the neural network to learn complicated patterns. The final product layer computes the prediction value of a specific class. The quantity of neurons in this level usually corresponds to the number of classes in the classification task which indicates that the volume of neurons in this layer is equal to the number of classes in the classification task. However, for a binary classification (two classes) one output neuron is used instead of two and is typically accompanied by a Sigmoid activation function. Sigmoid linearizes the raw output logit and maps it into the range between 0 and 1, which means that if the output is greater than a threshold (usually 0.5), we classify the input as belonging to the positive class; otherwise, it falls into the negative class. Whenever there are more than two classes, the Softmax function is usually applied. Softmax is the function that changes the raw scores (logits) into a probability distribution over all classes so that each output neuron is the probability of the input belonging to its class.

The Softmax function is defined as:

$$Softmax(Z_i) = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^k e^{z_j}}$$

Where (z_i) is the raw score for class (i), and (K) is the total number of classes

The Sigmoid function is defined as:

$$Sigmoid(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

Where x is the input to the function and e is the base of the natural logarithm (approx 2.71828)

A.5. Traditional CNN

Figure 10 is a representation of the layers present in a traditional CNN model. In this study, we constructed a custom CNN model. The model consists of: 3 Convolutional Layers (Conv2D), 3 Max Pooling Layers (MaxPooling2D), 1 Flatten Layer (Flatten), 2 Fully Connected Layers (Dense), and 1 Dropout Layer (Dropout). The input size is (256, 256, 3), representing an image size of 256x256 pixels, and 3 color channels (RGB). Since the main data set consists of only two classes: scam and non-scam, we consider this task as a binary classification. In a binary classification task a single neuron with a sigmoid activation function outputs a probability value between 0 and 1 each value corresponds to a specific class, in this case a probability value of 0 is considered as a non-scam while 1 is considered as a scam. We also added a dropout layer before the last dense layer in order to avoid overfitting. Overfitting usually occurs when the model generalizes too well on the training dataset that it fails to recognize unseen data while underfitting occurs when the model fails to learn robust image features, both underfitting and overfitting can lead to incorrect predictions or low accuracy. Techniques such as dropout prevents these types of errors during classification, dropout allows the model to not rely solely on the training data set by applying a term or penalty to each neuron, for example: a dropout of 0.5 indicates that 50% of the neurons will be randomly dropped out on each training iteration, this will allow the model to learn more robust features of the data set which will significantly increase the model's accuracy.

Fig 10. Traditional Approach

A.6. Model Evaluation

In evaluating the performances of the 3 models, the following accuracy metrics are used in order to provide insights about the performances of each area such as scam and non-scam accuracy, overall accuracy, mcc, and f-1 score.

1. **Scam Accuracy:** The Scam Accuracy measures the proportion of correctly identified scam cases.

$$\text{Scam Accuracy} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

2. **Non-Scam Accuracy:** The Non-Scam Accuracy measures the proportion of correctly identified non-scam cases.

$$\text{Non - Scam Accuracy} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

3. **Overall Accuracy:** The Overall Accuracy measures the proportion of all cases (both scam and non-scam) that have been correctly classified.

$$\text{Overall Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

4. **Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC):** The MCC (Matthews Correlation Coefficient) provides a more informative measure of binary classification performance than accuracy, particularly when classes are of different sizes. It considers all elements of the confusion matrix for a balanced assessment.

$$MCC = \frac{(TP \times TN) - (FP \times FN)}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}}$$

5. **F1-score:** The F1-score is a single metric that combines precision and recall, providing a more balanced evaluation of a classification model's performance, especially in cases with imbalanced data. It is calculated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall.
- 6.

$$f - 1 \text{ Score} = 2 \times \frac{TP}{2TP + FP + FN}$$

A.7. Accuracy and Loss

Loss: This metric measure how well the model is doing. It represents the summation of errors in the model. If the errors are high, the loss will be high, indicating that the model is not performing well. Conversely, a lower loss indicates a better performing model. The loss is calculated using a loss or cost function, it penalizes errors in different ways depending on the classification problem.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{(x,y) \in D} (y - \text{prediction}(x))^2$$

Where N is the total number of examples in the dataset D, y is the actual value, and prediction(x) is the predicted value

Accuracy: This metric measure how well the model predicts by comparing the model predictions with the true values in terms of percentage. While loss and accuracy are correlated, with decreasing loss often leading to increased accuracy, they provide different perspectives on the model's performance.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

Where TP = True Positives, TN = True Negatives, FP = False Positives, and FN = False Negatives

A.8. Confusion Matrix

A confusion matrix is a tool that summarizes the performance of a machine learning model on a test data set. It displays the number of accurate and inaccurate instances based on the model's predictions in a grid like structure. The matrix includes:

True Positives (TP): This is when the model correctly identifies a scam.

True Negatives (TN): This is when the model correctly identifies a non-scam.

False Positives (FP): This is when the model incorrectly identifies a non-scam as a scam.

False Negatives (FN): This is when the model incorrectly identifies a scam as a non-scam.

The confusion matrix is particularly useful in evaluating a model's performance beyond basic accuracy metrics, especially when there is an uneven class distribution in a dataset.

B. Application Development

Figure 14. TensorFlow Mobile and TensorFlow Lite

In Machine Learning, methodical steps that are adhered to during model development and deployment into production have to be well defined. Firstly, building a keras model which is a high-level neural networks library for doing sophisticated computation is done. This model is trained on a data set most pertinent until it meets the acceptable accuracy thresholds. After training is finished, the model is saved in the Hierarchical Data Format version 5 (H5), which is a popular format for storing large arrays of numerical data. This format is mainly helpful for retaining the model's architecture and weights to avoid any loss during the saving procedure. Likewise, the model is converted to the TensorFlow Lite format to deploy it on a mobile platform, in an Android application. TensorFlow Lite is a streamlined product that allows model training to take place on mobile devices and in embedded appliances. Conversion is smoothed through the model converter in TensorFlow Lite that optimizes the model for mobile devices with limited resources. The Android App is written in Java using the Android Studio integrated development environment (IDE). Android Studio environment ensures a stable and powerful platform for coding, debugging,

designing the user interface of the application, and testing on virtual or physical devices. In the application, the TensorFlow Lite Interpreter API is used for loading and running the model. The API serves as the interface between the application and the model thus being able to execute predictions. The architecture for the application is designed to work completely in an offline mode. This functional area is very important for maintaining privacy for users and also efficiency of the app. Local processing of data on the device promotes lower latency and allows for avoiding the sharing of data, thus ensuring user privacy.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A.1. Model Evaluation Results

Table 1. Model Accuracy and Hyperparameters

CNN Variant	Hyperparameters	Feature Selection Algorithm Used	Accuracy in Predicting Scam	Accuracy in Predicting Non-Scam	Overall Accuracy	MCC Score	F- score
(2nd) Custom CNN	Input Size=(254, 254, 32), Hidden Layers=(3 Convolutional Layers, 3 MaxPooling Layers, 2 Dense Layers),Output Layer=1,Epochs=35, Activation Function= Sigmoid,Dropout rate=0.5, Learning Rate: Default	Non	0.9203	0.9067	0.9120	0.828	0.910
(3rd) Mobile Net V3 (Small)	Include_top=False, Input Size=(224, 224, 3), Hidden Layers=2 Dense Layers,Output Layer=1,Epochs=35, Activation Function= Sigmoid,Dropout rate=0.5, Learning Rate: Default	Non	0.926	0.868	0.896	0.794	0.903
(1st) Mobile Net V2	Include_top=False, Input Size=(224, 224, 3), Hidden Layers=2 Dense Layers,Output Layer=1,Epochs=50, Activation Function= Sigmoid,Dropout rate=0.5, Learning Rate: Default	Non	0.9403	0.9026	0.9201	0.842	0.914

After comparing the performance of the three models: Mobile Net V2, Mobile Net V3 (Small), and Custom CNN. The results suggest that:

Mobile Net V2 (With transfer learning): This model demonstrated superior performance, achieving an overall accuracy of **92.01%**. It was particularly effective in classifying scams with an accuracy of **94.03%**, and showed a great performance in identifying non-scams with an accuracy of **90.26%**. The Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) score of **0.842** and an F-1 score of **91.4%** further attest to the model's robustness and its ability to maintain a harmonious balance between precision and recall.

Custom CNN (Without transfer learning): Although this model did not outperform Mobile Net V2, it still showcased a respectable performance. It achieved an overall accuracy of **91.20%**, with a **92.03%** accuracy in classifying scams and **90.67%** in classifying non-scams. The MCC score of **0.828** and an F-1 score of **91%**, although slightly lower than Mobile Net V2 still indicates a a good balance of precision and recall.

Mobile Net V3 (Small) (With transfer learning): This model, while not as effective as the other two still managed to achieve an overall accuracy of **89.6%**. It had an accuracy of **92.6%** in classifying scams and **86.8%** in classifying non-scams. However, the MCC score of **0.794** and an F-1 score of **90.3%** were the lowest among the three models, indicating a less optimal balance between precision and recall.

In summary, all three models demonstrated commendable performance. However, the Mobile Net V2 model, with transfer learning, emerged as the most effective model in terms of accuracy, MCC score, and F-1 score. The Model without transfer learning and with transfer learning is further evaluated.

A.2. Accuracy and Loss of The Top Performing Models

(a) Mobile Net V2

(b) Custom CNN

Figure 12. Loss and Accuracy Comparison between model (a) and (b)

In comparing the loss and accuracy of the model **(a) Mobile Net V2** and **(b) Custom CNN** different patterns can be observed. Mobile Net V2 demonstrates a rise in accuracy nearing 1.0 indicating its good performance. The loss rate for Mobile Net V2 decreases steadily and fluctuates but tends to stabilize around 0.2 indicating less errors in its predictions. Conversely Custom CNN shows that the accuracy graph steadily increases nearing 1.0 while the loss graph fluctuates but stabilizes around 0.3. While the accuracy of Custom CNN shows fluctuations with an increasing trend it is not as smooth as the Mobile Net V2. Similarly the loss values for Custom CNN did not stabilize effectively as compared to Mobile Net V2. These findings suggest that Mobile Net V2 outperforms Custom CNN in terms of accuracy and error reduction. The stable graphs of Mobile Net V2 reflect its reliability and effectiveness in applying learned patterns in classifying unseen data which is suitable for scam classification.

A.3. Confusion Matrix of The Top Performing Models

(a) Mobile Net V2

(b) Custom CNN

Figure 13. Confusion Matrix Comparison between model (a) and (b)

In the confusion matrices presented in Figure 13, we can observe that the accuracy of the MobileNet V2 (a) and Custom CNN (b) models fluctuate. MobileNet V2 shows superiority in detecting non-scam instances, with 139 false negatives as opposed to 136 false negatives classified by the Custom CNN model. In addition, it also shows more instances of scams being identified as non-scams with 15 false negatives compared to the Custom CNN model's result of 14 false negatives. Unlike in the case of the Custom CNN (a) model, the Custom CNN (b) model has a higher accuracy in detecting actual scam instances, 127 true positives, compared to the 126 true positives classified by the MobileNet V2 model. With these variations presented, the MobileNet V2 model's overall performance is better than the Custom CNN model that made 25 misclassifications compared to the Mobile Net V2 which has 23 misclassifications.

B.1. Application Interface

Figure 15. Main Menu Interface

The Scam Guard Application is designed with a user-centric interface (Fig. 15) that facilitates interaction through three primary functions, each represented by a distinct button within the main menu as shown in Figure 15: 'Image Classification', 'Guard Bot', and 'Settings'.

Image Classification Functionality: The pre-trained TensorFlow model will be loaded into the environment when the 'Image Classification' button is clicked. This model is a complex neural network being input to accomplish a task of binary classifications. After the user uploads an image, the model takes over and processes the data before assigning a prediction score. The prediction score is a calculated score which is based on the likelihood of the picture containing recognisable elements of a scam. The threshold mechanism of this class is based on a 50% or 0.5 threshold. Predictions scores at, or below this point are categorized as Class 0, which means non-scam, while scores higher than this point are recognized as Class 1, which represents a scam. Efficient categorisation is one of the key factors within the applications effectiveness, letting users determine probabilities of a message screenshot being a scam or not.

Guard Bot Feature: The 'Guard Bot' button will redirect users to a chat interface that is interactive and prepared by a JSON algorithm. This code has the capability to browse the keywords and phrases that are characteristic of scam-related inquiries in the user input. According to the key words, the chatbot generates answers to guide users, letting them know about scams, which increases their ability to detect fraudulent activities and avoid them.

Settings and User Feedback: The settings button allows easy access to user's processes that help them customize the experience within the application. Users can change their username, send feedback and comments to the program developers of the application and can see more information about the application. The feedback feature allows users to evaluate the application, inform us about errors, bring ideas and take part in improving the application.

Figure 16. Image Classification Interface

In the Image Classification Interface there are two buttons namely: “Upload Image” and the “Predict” button. In addition, there is also an image view in order for the user to view the uploaded image. The Upload Image button allows the users to upload an image, specifically a screenshot of a message. After the user has uploaded an image the user will be able to crop, rotate, zoom, and resize the image, this feature is added into the application in order for the region of interest inside the image to be focused allowing the tensorflow lite model to predict the image accurately. Lastly, the Submit button will allow the user to directly send the image inside the tensorflow API which preprocesses the image and finally calculates a prediction value. The prediction value which is stored inside the tensorflow API is then displayed together with its confidence value or the prediction value. If the uploaded image is predicted as “Scam” the prediction value must be above a threshold value of 0.5 otherwise it is classified as “Non-scam”. To make the interface more intuitive we added a small feature that turns the text red if the prediction is scam and green if the image is non-scam. Overall, the Image Classification Interface provides the user an easy to navigate interface allowing it to be straightforward and easy to understand.

Figure 17. Guard Bot Interface

In the Guard Bot Interface there is a “Submit” button, an input box above, and output box below. The input box allows the user to type in a prompt or query related to scams. When the user inputs a prompt and selects the “Submit” button the prompt is preprocessed and sent inside the predefined JSON library which contains keywords and responses. After the response is preprocessed and scanned for keywords, the predefined chatbot returns a response coming from the predefined JSON library and inside the output box below the response is displayed. In order to make the interface more intuitive we added a small feature which adds a typing animation. While this predefined chatbot is beneficial when it comes to offline environments it also has a slight disadvantage over an artificial intelligence powered chatbot mainly because the predefined chatbot has a limited amount of responses. Despite the disadvantage adding this feature adds more functionality inside the application and reduces privacy concern since the responses are already predefined; there are no server to server interactions which is sometimes the cause of private information being leaked. Overall, the Guard Bot Interface offers a straightforward interface allowing users to type in queries and get responses directly without requiring internet connectivity.

In the Settings interface there are 3 distinct buttons namely: “Provide Feedback” for feedbacking purposes, “Edit Username” for editing the username, and “About” this is where additional information about the app is displayed. Inside the “Provide Feedback” button is a google form link that redirects user to a user evaluation form. This evaluation form is adopted from the Mobile Application Rating Scale (MARS), a standard instrument that was first devised by Stoyanov and his colleagues and used to examine the quality of health-related mobile applications. Their study, "Mobile App Rating Scale: The 2015 article, "A New Tool for Assessing the Quality of Health Mobile Apps", where MARS was presented as a comprehensive approach to appraisal across multiple dimensions, a new method for evaluating the quality of mobile health apps was introduced. Our adaptation of the MARS questionnaire for the Scam Guard Application involved customizing 23 items or questions to measure the application’s quality across six key areas: engagement, functionality/interaction, appearance/aesthetics, information quality, subjective

quality, and perceived impact. Similarly, each question is rated using a 5-point Likert scale, having the value of 1 (Inadequate) to 5 (Excellent), monitoring the detailed evaluation of the app.

Figure 18. Settings Interface

Figure 19. Feedback Loop

Figure 19 represents a feedback loop in Scam Guard’s development process. It begins with the “User Feedback” where users share their experiences and suggestions about the application such as the features and the scam classification capabilities. The feedback is then “Received” and analyzed to identify areas for improvement. The insights coming from the users are applied in the “Improve Application” stage enhancing the application’s user interface and scam detection capabilities. This iterative process ensures that the application continually adapts to the users needs and the evolving landscape of online security.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This study proposes an Android application for classifying scam messages in the form of screenshots. We presented two Mobile Net architectures as well as fine-tuning the Custom CNN to choose the ideal model to integrate inside the application for deployment. The results showed that the Mobile Net V2 architecture performed better than the Mobile Net V3 (Small) and the Custom CNN. In addition, the results showed that the Custom CNN model can be a rival to the already existing transfer learning models (this does not mean that a Custom CNN is more superior to a Transfer Learning Model architecture), this only means that this type of classification problem, especially in our novel dataset, requires a dedicated CNN model mainly because the images contained in the dataset are non-natural as compared to the imagenet dataset, which contains images of animals, objects, and people and not screenshots of messages.

Mobile Net V2, which is the top performing model, was then converted into a lite version using the conversion capabilities of TensorFlow lite, which was then quantized and integrated using Android Studio IDE with Java language as the main programming language. The Performance of the Mobile Net V2 showed that out of all the 288 test images there were only 23 misclassifications achieving an overall accuracy of 92%.

Furthermore, since this application is only supported for Android devices, we aim to add support for the application to ios-devices in our future work. With this, Android users can not only leverage machine learning capabilities in detecting scams, but also ios users.

In conclusion, this study contributes to the already existing body of knowledge about scam detection most importantly here in the Philippines. Since our data set is novel in our future work, we aim to further enhance scam detection capabilities by gathering more data and experimenting with different approaches. We believe that this application will allow the elderly and young people to be empowered when it comes to making choices in the digital landscape, specifically when encountering messages.

Funding: This research was financially supported for publishing by the SRCB Office of the Research, Planning and Development.

Acknowledgments: The authors express gratitude to the anonymous reviewers for their valuable feedback and the SRCB Research, Planning and Development Office.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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